

PERSPECTIVE

From data to knowledge – big data needs stewardship, a plant phenomics perspective

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SUMMARY

The research data life cycle from project planning to data publishing is an integral part of current research. Until the last decade, researchers were responsible for all associated phases in addition to the actual research and were assisted only at certain points by IT or bioinformaticians. Starting with advances in sequencing, the automation of analytical methods in all life science fields, including in plant phenotyping, has led to ever-increasing amounts of ever more complex data. The tasks associated with these challenges now often exceed the expertise of and infrastructure available to scientists, leading to an increased risk of data loss over time. The IPK Gatersleben has one of the world's largest germplasm collections and two decades of experience in crop plant research data management. In this article we show how challenges in modern, data-driven research can be addressed by data stewards. Based on concrete use cases, data management processes and best practices from plant phenotyping, we describe which expertise and skills are required and how data stewards as an integral actor can enhance the quality of a necessary digital transformation in progressive research.

Keywords: data stewardship, FAIR data, plant phenomics, research data.

INTRODUCTION

Acquisition and evaluation of experimental data is at the heart of all empirical research. The reproducibility of findings is an important hallmark to the validity of scientific advances. In the life sciences, the technological progress of the last decades has increased the depth and volume of the generated data many times over. This, in combination with the 'publish or perish' environment of academic research (Miller et al., 2011), has resulted in the so-called 'reproducibility crisis', where most scientific results are difficult or even impossible to replicate (or often even just to reproduce) due to limited data accessibility, poor documentation of analytical methods and e.g. software-specific data formats (Baker, 2016; Ioannidis, 2005). In response, there has recently been a growing emphasis on making results available and reproducible for the long term by sharing accompanying data in a FAIR way (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Open and FAIR data is considered a critical asset in worldwide research. This value is reflected not only in various funding measures (de Almeida et al., 2017; Harrow et al., 2021; Hartl et al., 2021; Tauch & Al-Dilaimi, 2019),

infrastructure programmes, government strategies (Deutsche Bundesregierung, 2021) or binding regulations (Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2019), but also in the transformation of research data management (RDM) standards into norms, such as the aforementioned FAIR data sharing principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) or minimal information standards (Papoutsoglou et al., 2020). For example, the ISO technical report (ISO Central Secretary, 2021) of the International Organisation for Standardisation summarises the general principles of data sharing, introduces definitions of basic concepts, outreach to examples of existing standards and concludes major challenges to address in a potential formulated standard. Data sharing is a dissemination task of the research data life cycle of integral significance for preservation and publication of research work.

Various initiatives have also addressed the issue of how the FAIR requirements can be fulfilled and implemented in practice of the common data management process (Hausen et al., 2020; Jetten et al., 2021; Mayer et al., 2021; Scholtens et al., 2019). In our experience, the burden to fulfil the FAIR requirements is often left to the primary researchers generating them, who may be experts in their respective

subject fields but usually do not have the required training in data management and little motivational incentive to acquire it. In the absence of defined infrastructures and guidelines, researchers tend to be forced to develop their own management systems and data organisation structures, which are often incompatible with existing infrastructures and databases, leading to a loss of data over time (Fillinger et al., 2019; Li & Chen, 2014; Vines et al., 2014).

In this article, we explore the concept of data stewardship as a possible antidote to that conundrum and present lessons learnt, developed concepts and examples from the last two decades of RDM in plant phenotyping. This perspective is based on experiences and activities at the Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK). The IPK is an internationally leading plant scientific institute with the main research topics biodiversity and performance of crop plants. The distinguished gene bank of the IPK preserves about 151 000 different samples of genetic material, so-called accessions. By expanding the digital information services via the integration of genetic and phenotypic information with the help of bioinformaticians, data experts and data managers, the institute is developing into a bio-digital resource centre. High-throughput phenotyping in particular will play an increasingly important role in this process.

Phenomics is the systematic study of phenotypes. Nowadays, it has become an interdisciplinary field of research combining biology, data science, image analysis and engineering for qualitative and quantitative description of phenotypic traits of the investigated organism. Specifically, phenotypic traits resulting from genotypes and the environment are studied. This is a very important way to understand the interactions between the genetic background and the environment the plant develops in and its management ($G \times E \times M$), which is of course a major application in plant breeding (Araus et al., 2018; Pieruschka & Schurr, 2019; Tian et al., 2021; Watt et al., 2020), which tries to attain specific phenotypes of interest, such as increased yield or resilience to environmental stressors. In this article we will mainly focus on automated high-throughput phenotyping in controlled environments. Central challenges in phenomics are the different data domains and the inherent heterogeneity of multimodal data (Figure 1) and the fact that unlike laboratory analytics with established standard processes (Mayer et al., 2021), phenotyping is based on an agile empiricism that enables and often requires adaptation even within ongoing experiments. For example, a researcher might adjust the watering regime mid-experiment or decide to cut out flowering shoots. This unpredictability is caused by the large number and diversity of observable and quantifiable parameters, the variety of methods and protocols and the long-term nature of phenotyping experiments, which makes a FAIR-compliant data description and data management more challenging (Andrés-Hernández et al., 2021).

In addition to the complexity of the data, the multitude of actors involved in a plant phenotyping project can pose a significant challenge to consistent data management, unless communication and coordination between them takes into account their differences in knowledge level and expectations. As a simplistic model, here are four factors that can become relevant when collaborating on a data management project:

- **Data management skills:** Scientists with a technical or data modelling specialisation, either through their primary field of research or acquired separately, are usually familiar with concepts from the realm of FAIR data and have the technical expertise to implement them. So they will handle their data very differently from the stereotypical biologist who spends most of their time in the lab or on the field and uses Excel or other common tools to store their data. They are also likely to think about the data in more abstract terms which can lead to misunderstandings and difficulties in communication.
- **Familiarity with the institution's infrastructure:** Employees who are familiar with the established processes and resources their institute provides can often manage and publish their data in a FAIR and consistent way even if they themselves would not have the technical skills to set up or implement these infrastructures. Further, even a well-versed data manager can end up doing redundant or irrelevant work if they are not familiar with the resources that have already been established. This is often a problem when there is no dedicated person who informs newcomers about the established infrastructure and makes sure everybody uses it. Especially universities and large research institutes, which have a very broad research spectrum, can provide only a very limited general assistance.
- **Subject domain knowledge:** Conversely to the data management skills, the primary researcher working on a biological problem often has extensive knowledge about the subject domain, which is equally relevant for building data models: what information is relevant, what degree of detail is needed to keep it reproducible? It is crucial that both areas of expertise are brought together.
- **Personality type:** Finally, the scientist's personality will have a big influence on how they handle and communicate about their data, and is often a larger source of problems than the subject knowledge and vocabulary gaps between participants in a collaborative project. Personality types are difficult to quantify accurately. One attempt that is often used in employment or academic contexts (Poropat, 2009; Rothmann & Coetzer, 2003) is the 'Big Five' model (Digman, 1990), which describes personality in terms of five orthogonal traits: openness, conscientiousness, agreeableness, extraversion and neuroticism. From experience it seems plausible that conscientiousness and agreeableness are two particularly

Figure 1. Domains of plant phenotyping data. Four examples of data typically generated in a plant phenotyping experiment and their respective components are given. The photos are taken through non-invasive high-throughput imaging methods and related to rapeseed (*Brassica napus*). Raw Image Data (from left to right): Computer tomography, nuclear magnetic resonance and hyperspectral images of rapeseed seeds and a container from the IPK PhenoSphere (IPK-PS). Image-Derived Traits (from left to right): Fluorescence camera device, pictures of rapeseed seedlings with visible, near-infrared and fluorescence devices and the results after analysing the fluorescence camera picture. Environmental Data (from left to right): top view picture of a container in the IPK-PS, a temperature graph from the IPK-PS and a field drone picture from the AVATARS-Project. Metadata: metadata documents and the soil structure of a container in the IPK-PS.

important traits for the consistent, accurate outcome and extensive collaboration which are required but the exact role and relevance of each of the five traits in the context of data stewardship could be a valuable subject of future research.

The domain-specific aspects as well as the interpersonal communication challenges can only be mastered if an end-to-end data stewardship process is implemented and consistently executed – ensuring the ability to efficiently capture, curate and access large amounts of data (Peng et al., 2016). The professional and technical skills are required to implement concrete RDM activities. It is evident that tasks in these three areas of expertise must be solved

as a whole. This appears to be already common practice in many industrial contexts but is still lagging behind in academia and science. It cannot be solved selectively through technology, capacity building, organisational measures, self-obligations, standards and funding programmes for research data infrastructure (RDI). Rather, it requires coherent efforts, i.e. a mature data stewardship concept.

THE RENAISSANCE OF DATA STEWARDSHIP

Even though the term 'data stewardship' has become very popular in the last few years, it has deep roots and a long tradition in science (Rosenbaum, 2010). Data stewardship combines all efforts which are required to preserve and improve the information content and the usability of data

and metadata (Peng, 2018). Data stewards have the expertise to effectively and efficiently record, curate and facilitate access to large volumes of data (Hartter et al., 2013). They create the link between researchers, who produce and analyse research data, data managers, who define policies and standards describing metadata formats and data exchange pipelines, and policy makers, like PIs, funding agencies, journals or governance bodies.

In the current literature (e.g. Brous et al., 2016; Rosenbaum, 2010), the term 'data stewardship' is frequently used in combination with data governance, which can cause misunderstandings. Basically, data stewardship comprises (i) handling and quality monitoring of research data as assets and (ii) guaranteeing the accessibility of data with high quality for the corresponding community. In contrast, data governance describes the activities of defining general policies, recommendations, concepts and responsibilities for data stewardship (Rosenbaum, 2010). Data stewardship has been considered a part of data management within the scope of data governance with the aim to manage, curate and serve data depending on user needs. It is challenging and encompasses all tasks to preserve and improve the accessibility and usability of data as well as to enable linking between datasets within or across domains (Peng et al., 2018).

Major tasks and responsibilities

The previously mentioned aspects of a new digital expertise have led to new job profiles, such as research software engineer, data scientist, data curator, data manager, data librarian and just those of the data steward. These are not yet well established in terms of dedicated career and education paths, or role in perception in science, like for reputation, recognition and authorship. The tasks and positions of data stewards in the various organisations are also quite versatile. The involvement of data stewards is mainly based on the existing structures and local conditions. A concrete definition of the tasks does not exist, and integration of or differentiation from the above-mentioned roles in data management does not tend to take place (Hausen et al., 2020). These are objectives of ongoing initiatives (Jetten et al., 2021; Scholtens et al., 2019; Verheul et al., 2019). Rather, the current classification is closer to science-related support, which is also referred to as 'embedded data steward' (Kvale, 2021). For this reason, we would like to contribute to the current discourse by means of a list of tasks and core competencies.

Data curation. Data stewards take care of the data management and support the different steps in the data life cycle. They collect and curate the data and identify possible issues. Therefore data stewards handle the communication with the data producers to solve problems and improve the data life cycle, because in the end they are responsible for fulfilling the data quality standards and data structures from the

scientific perspective as well as the data conformance due to valid data policies (Baker & Yarmey, 2009; Walek, 2019). This work is very diverse and strongly depends on the current data domain, but some general tasks are checking sample names and IDs, controlling data transition processes and inspecting data file structures and formats.

In order to identify syntactic data errors, broken data files or other possible data consistency issues, it is necessary to establish constant monitoring at the different data life cycle and data transfer steps. General consistency checks such as calculating and controlling the checksums of the individual data files as well as data format-specific validation checks need to be performed to protect against systematic errors. Typical examples are automatic schema validation routines for machine-readable formats like XML and JSON or domain-specific metadata schema like MIAPPE (Papoutsoglou et al., 2020).

In addition, a logical data check is ideally performed by a data steward in order to detect semantic data content errors. Typical examples are wrong units or values, which do not make sense, e.g. two metres of measured plant height are plausible for maize plants but do not make sense for barley or wheat and indicate an error in the data acquisition. Doing this manually can be very difficult and time consuming, but there are some data quality concepts and theories which can be helpful to set up several automated checking routines (Schmidt et al., 2021; Wang & Strong, 1996).

Training and education. We are living in the big data age (Chen et al., 2013) and data management skills are an essential prerequisite to conduct successful and transparent research. However, most graduate programmes in life sciences do not address that requirement sufficiently. This change in education programmes will need some time but nevertheless a permanent enhancement of these data-related skills is necessary due to the constant development of methods, standards and software later when scientists do their actual research. Thus, beside the conceptual work, curation tasks and communication, data stewards also have to perform practical workshops and develop training material, e.g. data- and task-specific tutorials, for the data producers and scientists who work with the data. Usually not all scientists, at least not from the beginning, are familiar with common metadata schemas like MIAPPE (Papoutsoglou et al., 2020) or data formats like ISA-Table (Sansone et al., 2012) and confident with established institutional management systems or external repositories. Regular training and long-term support for the scientists about developed formats and established data infrastructures and tools to store their data will guarantee data completeness and quality when they want to publish and share the data later. The same skills are crucial for retrieval and reuse of public data, thus contributing to the quality and thoroughness of the research process.

Orchestration. Finally, yet importantly, data orchestration is another part of data stewardship, which is the process of taking the different pieces of data from multiple storage locations and transforming and organising them for efficient data analysis. Therefore, it is necessary to transform data from different formats to an unambiguous, standardised format, which can be directly used by the analysis pipelines. This could be general data format transformations like transferring files from XML or CSV into JSON format, but also single data point transformations like using the same numerical format for dates or the same measurement units for sizes within all data files.

Personal strengths and required skills

As a result of the role as intermediary between the different data domains and different data storage levels in the data life cycle, data stewards need a certain expertise within the subject areas, like knowledge of established metadata formats or process definitions to guarantee community-accepted quality standards. Furthermore, this also requires a relatively high technical understanding from a data steward, such as the functioning of established infrastructures and databases, used exchange protocols or basic programming skills. The daily improvement of data technologies and methods requires multidisciplinary and technical knowledge (Peng et al., 2018) as well as continuous education.

Besides the technical skills, soft skills are just as important, because the data steward has a tight connection with the involved researchers and administrators in every step of the RDM process. Data stewards are usually the first contact in case of any problems. Therefore excellent communication and negotiation skills are required. Furthermore, data stewards need comprehensive documentation and presentation skills to explain complex processes to the researchers and teach them how to use specific tools or how to follow established standards and formats. Depending on the complexity and interdisciplinarity of the research data domains it can be useful or rather necessary to work with a team of data stewards, who have different, but complementary expertises, because comprehensive cross-domain knowledge can be very challenging for a single person. This also requires good teamwork and strong organisational capabilities.

Even though the data steward as a role has only come into prominence over the last decade, there are already advanced examples of data stewardship in domain-overarching as well as domain-specific initiatives, particularly in the domains of health, plant and earth sciences, which are mentioned in the following section.

STATE OF THE ART

In the life sciences, there has been a considerable amount of work done on the concept of data stewardship. One

notable example is the ELIXIR-Netherlands supported project 'Towards FAIR Data Steward as a profession for the Lifesciences'. In the project report (Scholtens et al., 2019), the main focus of a data steward is defined by three different data steward roles that can be defined ('policy', 'research' and 'infrastructure'). For all three data steward roles, eight competence areas were defined. The responsibilities and tasks in these eight competence areas can be seen as different aspects of the function that the data steward has. Furthermore, data stewardship is also a deeply anchored concept in RDI programmes at the national level, e.g. the project DataPLANT (Von Suchodoletz et al., 2021) under the framework of NFDI (Bierwirth et al., 2020), whose ultimate objective is to establish procedures for the management of research data, to develop tools and to provide an infrastructure that will enable such collaborative research in plant biology, and also at the international level, e.g. the Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group (PDS-IG) of the Research Data Alliance (RDA, <https://www.rd-alliance.org>) or the Committee on Data (CODATA) of the International Science Council. In a funding co-operation among CODATA and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) the pilot project 'terms4FAIRskills' moved the data steward terminology to support the creation and assessment of stewardship curricula, formalisation of job descriptions, etc. (European Commission, 2021).

In addition, the international community has made several efforts to help researchers adhere to data stewardship guidelines. One of the examples of a community-driven project is ELIXIR-Converge, an EU project responsible for standardising RDM in the life sciences (Harrow et al., 2021). The ELIXIR-Converge consortium has developed the Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit), an online best practice tool for data management that applies to research projects (RDMkit, 2021). The RDMkit contains guidelines, information and pointers to help researchers comprehend proper data stewardship during each phase of the life cycle.

The efficiency, comprehensibility and quality of information is a central factor in the sciences and is reflected in guidelines and codes of conduct. Special attention is devoted to areas with special quality requirements, such as health sciences (McGlynn et al., 2003), or sustainable data and information flows, as for globally relevant issues, such as the United Nations Convention of Biological Diversity (CBD) (CBD, 2015), Digital Sequence Information (DSI) (Aubry, 2019) and earth science data. Stewardship of health information enforces 'trust and competency; adoption of technology; and new models for data exchange (and new skills for managing health information) that include the patient as part of the data supply chain' (Rosenbaum, 2010).

In the example of DSI stewardship, parties to the CBD are debating a new benefit-sharing framework. It is

intended to incentivise access to and use of genetic resources so that benefits from use of biodiversity will flow back to the providing country. Recent papers suggest a complex information flow for DSI and high potential benefit resulting from reusability of DSI (Scholz et al., 2021) and argue to preserve open access as a crucial common good (Scholz et al., 2022).

Another example of data stewardship can be observed under the umbrella of the Federation of Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP). The ESIP has been practising data stewardship for the last 15 years and lately has established a data stewardship committee. The very first initiative of the committee was to recommend identifying technology that can be used to assess the potency of the earth science data. They come up with a set of recommendations, such as the use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), and develop data citation guidelines for publishing the datasets in all American Geophysical Union publications (Downs et al., 2015).

These prominent examples show the crucial concern is to maintain in data stewardship concepts a balance between data access and privacy and economic interests, which needs to be regulated by policymakers. A negotiation over the scope and terms of access and use need to consider all stakeholders and interests. Thus, stewardship entities should be federally chartered, with dedicated use-case and domain-specific authority to collect, prepare and support the use of research data.

Through these cornerstones of necessary activities to implement the FAIR criteria across all phases of the research data life cycle, it is evident that this is a cross-domain, collaborative task. This awareness was initially driven by rather practical aspects of data publication and reuse by researchers. However, it was reinforced by the increasing demands of research funders, databases and journals, and became manifested in the concept of data stewards. The concept of data stewardship has emerged in the discourse of RDM, and with the advent of national and international programmes to develop a sustainable infrastructure, like NFDI or ELIXIR, it has become increasingly significant for the life sciences. It is equally important that data stewards must have a very close connection to the respective subject domain, communication skills and technical expertise.

For plant phenotyping specifically, the most notable development so far is perhaps the aforementioned MIAPPE standard (Papoutsoglou et al., 2020), which is generally widely known and well accepted in the community and has been made part of standardisation efforts such as the ELIXIR RDMKit (RDMKit, 2021) introduced above. Thus, MIAPPE has provided a checklist (BioSamples, 2022a) which improves the description of the metadata and samples (BioSamples, 2022b) for the nucleotide sequences stored in the EMBL-ENA database (ENA, 2022). In the next

section, we will describe the history and current practice of data management and stewardship at our own institute and hopefully give some helpful insights for future developments in data stewardship for the plant phenotyping field.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND DATA STEWARDSHIP FROM A PLANT PHENOMICS PERSPECTIVE

In 2019, the IPK has made the strategic decision to evolve towards a bio-digital resource centre. This requires a transformation of heterogeneous RDM processes into a homogeneous overarching RDM life cycle. The defined roadmap consists of milestones that are monitored by the directors board. This comprises the definition of pilot groups and flagship projects to implement data stewardship measures for core domains, like genebank management (Weise et al., 2020), sequencing (Mayer et al., 2019) and phenomics (Bolger et al., 2019). Here, the nucleus is the IPK genebank, which has been an important source of genetic resources in the form of physical material for several decades, such as seeds, cryopreserved probes or plants (Oppermann et al., 2015). For the transformation to a leading bio-digital resource centre it will be necessary to integrate all the major digital information which is generated in the frame of the genebank-associated projects, such as genomic sequences, genotype information, weather, soil and nutrition data or phenotypic images, in a FAIR-compliant and sustainable way. Therefore, the transformation follows a three-phase approach:

First, a comprehensive assessment of existing databases, experimental analytics and data collection processes and analysis and dissemination pipelines as well as responsibilities and infrastructures is conducted. Secondly, these are consolidated technically and organisationally, resulting in core concepts and processes, which are then finally transferred into a sustainable operational and management framework in the coming years. In the following section, we will explain the current data management situation and data stewardship concepts at the IPK and outline some challenges and an example of a first implemented concept addressing them.

The roots of data management at the IPK

The first work on integrated data management at the IPK dates back to the development of databases for the management of genebank-relevant data (Knüpffer et al., 1995) and the first web information systems on molecular biological data (Pleissner et al., 1999). From 2002 onwards, the Bioinformatics Centre Gatersleben-Halle (BIC-GH) funding programme supported the development of RDIs and databases. Here, the first infrastructures were created and a common organisational structure was established to maintain and further develop the databases that had been created. The 'Genebank Information System' (Oppermann

et al., 2015), the 'Plant Data Warehouse for genotypic, phenotypic and expression data of cultivated plants' (Kuenne et al., 2007) and other databases that were created were ultimately precursors to the current institute strategy for developing a bio-digital resource centre. This required the transition from personally managed files and heterogeneous information systems towards a centrally organised storage management. The lessons learnt in the late 1990s and early 2000s in respect of RDM and software development led to a realignment of the RDI and processes to implement a vital and long-term sustainable RDM life cycle (Arend et al., 2014).

Electronic lab notebook and information management system. Over 10 years ago, the IPK established an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) and a laboratory information management system (LIMS) as a general platform for documenting and recording all kinds of research data created in the lab or in the field. The core data modules consist of the hierarchical relationship of projects, experiments, samples, measurements, parameters and methodology descriptions. They cover around 80% of the use cases. This is flanked by several domain-specific data capture and ingestion processes to implement the RDM life cycle along the FAIR principles. Import functions and a hybrid online/offline client-server architecture allow to store extensive information such as sequence data or phenotypic images, and also scalar values such as sensor data or phenotypic values. The graphical user interface (GUI) is generic and can be adapted to implement users with regard to operation and layout. Machine-readable access is provided via an open, well-documented SQL interface (Ghaffar et al., 2020). This flexibility means that, in principle, all data generated in projects can be stored, but it also requires regular training and supervision of the scientists and technical assistants in terms of the data and metadata standards to be applied and the utilisation of the GUI for data input and retrieval.

Project-related web portals. The LIMS showed convincing benefit as a universal platform for data management of complex RDM processes. As of October 2021 it is the home of around 17 million results and over 5 million samples on various plant materials. A project proprietary database and private file-based data stores have been replaced stepwise and a harmonised data management system has been implemented across various research and services projects. Nevertheless, LIMS cannot solely technically meet all project requirements and FAIR principles. The harmonisation of data and semantic metadata is a challenge that has to be addressed by common data quality and consistency measures, which is the objective of an institute-wide data stewardship programme. Furthermore, project-specific data interfaces and visualisations require programming efforts

to develop specific web applications, APIs, data warehouses and search portals to make data findable and accessible for humans and machines. The interoperability and reusability in respect of semantic data and metadata harmonisation is addressed by sophisticated data flow processes within the LIMS. The implementation and process specification can be quite time consuming. Usually the developer needs to spend time to learn about the project-specific data structure and organisation within the LIMS and also needs to understand the context and semantics of the data, which requires constant communication with the responsible project data manager.

In summary, the developed infrastructures and web portals have usually been very specifically focused on the needs of the respective project partners. As a result, the associated projects have been very successful, but disadvantages include the lack of sustainability, the low amounts of harmonised semantic data and metadata and the low focus on universal FAIR-compliant data dissemination. That could cause a notable risk for follow-up projects to invest potential avoidable resources in development and conceptual design of data management and curation processes.

Data publication pipeline. In the early 2010s, persistent IDs gained more and more acceptance in the scientific community. This is especially evident as DOIs have become an ISO standard and have been supported by a large number of publishers (Boudry & Chartron, 2017; Wang et al., 2018). This is also reflected at the IPK by its long-time membership in the DataCite consortium and its role as a registered data centre to mint DOIs for genebank accessions and e!DAL-PGP published data. While DataCite takes care of resolving DOIs and guaranteeing the long-term accessibility of the linked datasets, every data centre has the responsibility to organise and manage the persistent storage of data files. At the time there were no established and easy-to-use software solutions available for managing the DOI metadata and assigning of DOIs to in-house stored datasets. This caused a lot of individual, manual effort for organising the metadata templates and maintaining a web server for providing stable URLs that can be resolved by the registered DOIs. Furthermore the barrier for the scientists was very high, because they needed personal communication with the IT service to request a DOI for their research data. All these initial challenges resulted in only 20 DOIs registered over 3 years at the IPK. Therefore the conceptualisation of a light-weight and generic software infrastructure called e!DAL was started for handling research data and assigning DOIs in 2012. In 2014, an initial e!DAL version was released (Arend, Lange, et al., 2014) and subsequently improved until 2016. This year, the Plant Genomics and Phenomics Research Data Repository (e!DAL-PGP) as the first productive

instance was released, providing a FAIR-compliant infrastructure and integrated and peer review-based data publication pipeline (Arend et al., 2016). At the beginning the repository was limited to IPK users, but by following the on-premise approach and continuous improvement of the underlying e!DAL infrastructure, the PGP repository has been opened to external data publishers. It has already been accepted by several publishers, it is core infrastructure in German national and European research and infrastructure projects and it has already published 250 comprehensive and diverse plant search datasets (Arend et al., 2020) that comprise more than 1.5 million single files.

The present state of data management at the IPK

As mentioned before, the transformation of the IPK genebank and the complete institute into a bio-digital resource centre is catalysed by the genebank and driven by concrete research and infrastructure projects. These enable the systematic acquisition of a broad field of omics data. In particular, non-invasive high-throughput phenotyping under field and controlled conditions is an important part of data capture. Using a flagship project as a representative example, the current status of data management at the IPK will be shown.

An enabler project is 'Advanced Virtual and Augmented Reality Approaches in Seeds to Seeds' (AVATARS), which was launched in 2019 and runs until 2024 (<https://www.avatars-project.de>). The major goal of AVATARS is the development and utilisation of innovative concepts for data visualisation and exploration by using virtual and augmented reality in plant breeding and investigation of developmental processes in *Brassica napus* seeds. For these purposes, different experiments will be combined, such as field trials, growth regimes in controlled environments, 'omics' analyses (Vailati-Riboni et al., 2017) and imaging techniques. Furthermore, deep learning approaches will be used to predict germination capacity. The depth and throughput of data, as well as the diversity of data modalities and contribution of multiple labs, make AVATARS a model case for the necessity and implementation of a consequently lived data stewardship concept.

Within the project, the RDM aspects were addressed in a dedicated work package and organised along a consortium-wide agreed upon data management plan, which was driven forward with the narrative of a sustainable and integrated direction with a focus on providing FAIR, long-term preserved, open and integrated data. A federated RDI serves as backbone for dispersed data providers and data consumers in an agile and FAIR way. A developed data hub provides data and integrates structures and interfaces for high-performance data access paths, downstream data analysis and data sharing. In particular, the RDI provides a storage infrastructure to archive

and document project-related research data and a scalable and programmatic access to integrated and high-dimensional omics data. Both components were realised using the institutional hierarchical storage system and the previously mentioned LIMS.

This procedure was aligned with previous projects, but implemented more strictly data stewardship aspects to ensure a FAIR data management with high data consistency and data quality within the entire RDM life cycle. Figure 2 shows the general fields of activity of data stewards for RDM as well as the concrete steps which were executed for the data processing and handling within the AVATARS project. Subsequently some of the developed approaches are described in detail.

Digital twin concept. The basis for sustainable and effective data handling was the establishment of a digital twin (DT) concept, which is originally based on an approach for dovetailing complex industrial processes with accompanying digital processes (Vachalek et al., 2017). DTs are virtual copies of products or services and consist of a physical part and a virtual representation as well as a bridging connection between them (Portela et al., 2020).

For AVATARS, a project employee hired as IT engineer took over the role of data steward and intensely reviewed the planned data production and seed material logistics to adapt the DT concept to a data-intensive plant research project. The purpose of this role is to interlink physical material logistics, data acquisition and data ingestion processes to a previously agreed upon project-wide data flow. It covers all data flow aspects such as seed material tracking, observation data management, imaging and genotyping formats and storage and handling of gene expression and proteomics data.

The phase of data transfer from the project partners, i.e. the *collect phase* in the RDM life cycle, follows the data lake concept. A data lake is a centralised, volatile staging area that has been created to facilitate the upload of structured and unstructured data. We do this using an FTP server. These files are regularly assembled and uploaded by the partners themselves in ZIP archives and JSON files. The data files are structured and named following pre-specified specifications. In the *process phase*, driven by an observation daemon, several automatic checks, like validation of the file checksums, file names and ZIP archive integrity or a validation of JSON structured data, are done to ensure data consistency and completeness. After a successful data consistency check, the staged data files are inspected in respect of valid identifier, data structure or referential integrity by the AVATARS data steward and fed into the database import pipelines. In case of detection of ambiguous or invalid data files, the data steward is notified and will curate them or get in contact with the data provider in a feedback loop. To implement the *preservation*

Figure 2. Data stewardship tasks and AVATARS-specific implementation in the frame of the general Research Data Process.

phase, also called the *storage phase*, dedicated extract-transform-load (ETL) scripts transform structured data from JSON files and load them into the LIMS database backend. Binary files are moved to a file archive and linked in LIMS to the related DT object. To feature the *sharing phase*, all generated and curated datasets will be integrated and made accessible via a project data warehouse portal. This enables the packaging of related data into data containers according to the analysis context. This type of data reuse is especially intended for data analysis scenarios that rely on efficient high-throughput data access. Another reuse scenario is for pointwise access by a remote programmatic interface for on-demand data exploration and computation. API endpoints implement use case-specific requirements for online as well as offline data access scenarios that feature use cases for data visualisation as well as downstream data analysis pipelines.

The future of data management at the IPK

The presented approaches and ideas developed and tested in the frame of the AVATARS project can be used as an initial blueprint for future projects. Concepts like DT or the automatic file checksum test are quite intuitive and can be easily adapted to diverse research data workflows. Other automatic checks such as JSON validation strongly depend on the data domain and the technical opportunities for the used data formats. Nevertheless, we learnt that developing a suitable data consistency pipeline and quality assurance needs an experienced data steward who is familiar with the data domain for designing and controlling the process

together with the scientists, technicians and IT experts. Therefore, in the future, data stewardship needs to be considered an important task within comprehensive research projects and an integral part of every project proposal and the underlying data management plan as well as the general institutional research strategy. This will incur additional costs and implies the need to establish new concepts for long-term education and engagement of data stewards. Depending on the experiential settings and workflows, additional work is needed to design and coordinate data processes as well as organise and execute training courses for the different processing steps with the involved researchers and technicians.

Due to the high degree of specialisation and necessary work experience of data stewards, it is rather inefficient to hire a dedicated data steward for each granted project and then dismiss them again after the project has been finished. Therefore, scientists or technical staff are often appointed, who in normal circumstances need to do other work. Yet unfortunately, this is currently still the most common way in science. Project staff turn to temporary contracts and have to take over many of the tasks of a data steward while working on the actual project goals. It is necessary that a general rethinking takes place here, because an experienced data steward should be able to support multiple projects and workflows. Therefore, it might be a good approach for large and medium-sized research organisations to establish a stable group of data stewards with a permanent position. These could cover several research fields, or rather data domains, and could support

different projects in parallel, which over time would be very cost-effective and efficient. In addition, this would reduce the barriers for researchers and technicians to work with the data stewards and, at the same time, allow them to focus on their full project-related work.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this article, we provide an overview of the data stewardship challenges from a plant phenomics perspective. Most of them result from the strong heterogeneity of data types as well as the high degree of freedom due to the non-invasive characteristic of phenotypic experiments. The latter enables scientists to access the investigated plants and research material at any time. Usually, every phenotypic trial is well planned at the beginning, but the comparatively long experiment durations often lead to adjustments and course corrections during the execution phase, which can be challenging for data handling and guaranteeing data reproducibility. Sometimes, scientists tend to or even need to modify the experimental setup or parameters even when the actual trial is already running due to new insights or necessary adaptations based on new challenging conditions or errors. This is an important difference to other domains like genomics where we have established stable experimental workflows like DNA sequencing. Here it is possible to establish relatively fixed procedures for data description and data transfer and to define checks to control the different processing steps which guarantees data quality based on fixed conditions.

For the phenotypic data domain, a FAIR-compliant data description and data management is comparably challenging. Here it is necessary to establish flexible workflows with extensive data stewardship support to handle the high diversity of experimental settings and the broad data spectrum. We presented an exemplary approach, which was developed in the course of the AVATARS project. The concept was improved stepwise while the project was running and more and more data was produced. Here we realised that the tasks of the data steward were much more elaborate than initially expected, because the conceptualisation of the seed logistic as well as the establishment of the different technical steps is time consuming, but essential to identify bottlenecks and improve the procedures. Nevertheless, some of the developed approaches like the DT concept or automatic checksum tests can act as a blueprint for further projects and can be adapted to many other data domains. But of course other approaches like material logistic workflows or the data consistency validation pipeline strongly depend on the project background and the used data types. Therefore, it is usually necessary to spend additional effort for every project or workflow, but of course a well-trained and experienced data steward can reduce this and can benefit from previous developments and knowledge.

With the AVATARS project we showed one first example for the establishment of a project-wide data stewardship concept. One major difference in comparison to other past and present projects is the need for extensive data stewardship support that was already considered within the planning phase. This resulted in a dedicated work package, which is on the one hand responsible for the technical support during the project such as the extension of the institutional storage infrastructure and on the other hand takes care of FAIR data handling.

The IPK is one of the leading institutes for plant research and serves as host of one of the world's largest genebanks for crops. This significant infrastructure has been operating for almost 80 years. The staff are familiar with their tasks and the processes in long-term preservation including data management, especially in phenotyping. Besides the genebank, the IPK will extensively increase the work on phenotypic research and related projects. With the completion of the plant cultivation hall (currently being renamed to IPK PhenoSphere [IPK-PS]) (Langstroff et al., 2021), the IPK has a unique basis for running novel studies. With these new facilities and new technologies, the challenges have increased and the amount of data in phenotyping has multiplied. Here we face the same issues as the plant research community and the phenotyping community in general. New phenomics technologies and novel analysis procedures will not only provide new insights into plant developmental processes and produce a huge amount of data, but will further need a high investment into the development and implementation of a sufficient data stewardship strategy. This will be crucial to guarantee FAIR and sustainable data management to provide high-quality publications and valuable research data. It will be important to set up a successful concept for recruiting, training and keeping data stewards and change the established procedure of just thinking from one project to the next one, because as we recognised in the past, this cannot be sustainable and is usually more expensive from a long-term financial perspective.

Nevertheless, it can be difficult to estimate the average amount of effort and support of data stewardship that is needed for every project, because this strongly depends on the involved processes and the people working with the data. We tried to define a simplified model combining domain-specific and data modelling expertise, familiarity with the institution-specific resources and personality traits to evaluate the capability of individuals or teams in RDM projects. These factors are relevant based on our institutional and project-related experience but more rigorous empirical analyses are needed to determine if the model is appropriate for multiple use cases. One future goal could be developing an assessment space out of the four dimensions and shaping the required capability profile for a project team to determine the needed data stewardship support for a certain project. This could help to define data

management plans or profiles for data stewards and make it in general easier to organise and use them efficiently for specific RDM tasks.

Ultimately, in order to have a leading role in plant research and publish innovative science, it is necessary to be also a leader in handling the associated research data and providing FAIR and high-quality data.

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